

IMPACT OF E-LEARNING ON THE MOTIVATION AND RETENTION OF SOCIAL STUDIES STUDENTS IN UPPER BASIC SCHOOLS IN KWARA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: The research looked into the impact of e-learning in social studies students' motivation, retention and academic achievement in upper Basic schools in kwara state, Nigeria. The study was guided with four (4) research questions. A quasi-experimental design was used in this investigation. All upper basic school student in public schools totally 105,810 student was the target population. A total of 480 participants were chosen as sample size. The social studies performance test (SOSPET) was the instrument used in the resaerch. The instrument was validated b experts in statistics and language for content face and construct validity. A coeficient value of 0.79 was obtained for the social studies performance test using cronbach method. Discriptive statistics for mean and standard deviation were used to answer the question in this survey. The findings revealed that while using e-electronics, e-learners outperformed traditional learners. The findings of the study indicated that gender and school location hace imapct on students academic achievement. There was no difference in mean motivation scores between students who learned social studies through e-learning and those who learned thorough traditional methods, according to the research. Furhermore, the study discovered that students in Upper Basic Social Studies that were taught via e-learning had different mean retention rating than students that were taughts using traditional method. This means that employing e-learning technology help students to have a greater divesity of learning experiences while also presenting more information and enhancing retention. The Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) should change the curriculum at all level of Social Studies to fit the dynamic nature of e-learning technologies in all level of Upper School Social Studies classes. This will promote a student self discovery learning. Basic training on how to apply e-learning approaches should be provided to social studies teachers by Kwara State Government and Non – Governmental Organisation. This will benefit students' academic performance regardless of gender or location of Upper Basic School in the state.

Keywords: Impact, e-learning, motivation, retention, performance

Introduction

Education and learning are important processes for human development in society. To achieve this goal, the teaching / learning process must endure over time. One such way to do this is to use innovative 21st century education and learning strategies that reflect global education best practices. Therefore, scholars support e-learning because they believe it is best suited to the needs and characteristics of today's world (Amosa, Adelani & Adebola, 2015; Ngwu, 2015).E-Learning (EL) is the use of information and

communication technology. Strengthen education and learning activities such as the Internet, computers, mobile phones, learning management system "LMS", TV and radio. E-learning is a unified term used to describe areas of online learning, web-based training, and technology-enhanced education (Oye, Salleh & Iahad, 2010).

In any education system, the issue of student performance is very important in that school quality, teachers, and teaching methods determine the student's academic performance. According to Adeyemi (2011), academic

performance can be described as the level of education of a student at a particular point in time. The status of this academic achievement can be explained by the grades achieved in the course or group of courses. For this reason, individuals and organizations have worked together to ensure the best education system (Okon & Archibong, 2015). Despite these efforts, high school students' academic performance in social studies and other public school subjects remains very low, which is a concern for all educators in Kwara and throughout the country.

Social Studies is a social science subject taught at the level of primary education in Nigeria. This subject is the most popular social science at this level because it can teach learners the right attitudes, values and morals to be responsible citizens to actively contribute to the development of the country. It seems to be the subject. Social studies as a subject aims to provide the complete environmental experience that children need to live in the world. The subject develops appropriate skills and attitudes for learners and makes them patriots and contributors to the community (Ogundare, 2010; Olokooba & Abdulsalam, 2017). Despite the fact that social studies occupy an important position in our educational system, the study by Falade (2007) and Fagbemi, Gambari, Oyedum, and Gbodi (2012) asserted that traditional method of teaching and learning of social studies affect the performance of students in social studies in our educational system.

Yusuf (2007) confirmed this view when he admitted that social studies students were performing poorly due to inadequate teaching by teachers. Studies show that innovative teaching methods such as e-learning should affect student performance, motivation, and retention rates. However, rigorous evidence is limited. According to Lai, Sadoulet, and Janvry (2009), student grades are primarily explained by explaining teacher characteristics, while other variables such as motivation and retention play little role. Motivation is a positive attitude towards learning the subject, in addition to a combination of efforts and aspirations to achieve the learning goals. In short, learning motivation is related to the satisfaction that the student experiences in the activity and how much the student works or strives to learn for the desire to do so. Motivation helps to stimulate and guide students' abilities, allows them to learn and absorb

knowledge that will continue to be useful for future use, and academic performance is the result of internal permanence rather than external pressure. We guarantee that (GiampetroMeyer, 2012). From a cognitive psychology perspective, researchers define motivation as the process by which goal-oriented activities are initiated and maintained (McFerren, 2016).

The theory of multi-finality suggests that, depending on student motivation, those who start under similar conditions achieve different academic performance (Kruglanski, et al., 2013). As a result, different situations and teaching methods affect students in different ways. Far from questioning, e-learning is simply a process in which the learner "learns fishing", studying, planning, and studying, planning, in contrast to traditional methods where the philosophy of learning is dominant. Findings and interpretations are clues to active participation and help increase the retention rate of junior high school students in Social Studies. This is because e-learning involves activities that are interactive, flexible, and involve learners in knowledge building, active learning, and maintaining support. .. These types of activities are often associated with a quality learning experience, level of retention, and academic performance. (Koksal, Yagisan & Aksoy, 2013). However, gender differences can affect learner participation, retention, and achievement. Some studies suggest that women are superior to men when e-learning courses are designed to enable participation, interaction, and collaboration. This is because women prefer a more collaborative and interactive approach, and men take a more functional approach (Guiney, 2012).

Similarly, school location is also considered when examining student performance and retention levels in an innovative e-learning education strategy. Osalusi (2009) recognizes that rural students are witty in Hillbilly, with little education and an informed view of what is happening in the "real world." I reported that there is. Urban people, on the other hand, are more exposed to the latest technologies that can support learning than rural people. Therefore, it is important to study e-learning in relation to its impact on academic performance, retention, and motivation of higher social studies students.

Social studies is at the core of a high school curriculum designed to teach learners the right

attitudes, values, knowledge and skills to manage environmental resources for effective citizenship and maximum utilization. Educators and researchers have expressed serious concern about the status of social education and learning in secondary schools across the country, especially in Kwara. Studies show that only 10% of contents learned in the passive state (traditional teaching method) is retained after 30 days In the passive state or traditional teaching methods, the learner does not apply what he has learned (Timothy, 2008).

Objectives of the Study

The research aimed at looking on academic success of student in high school taught social studies using e-learning versus those taught using traditional method; to know the impact of gender and location by e-learning on the performance of social studies students in schools; identification of the impact of motivation on social studies students taught through the use of e-learning versus those taught with the traditional method and find out the effect of e-learning on the retention on the performance of social studies student.

Research Questions

- i. The following survey question has been created.
- ii. What is the academic performance of high school social studies students taught by e-learning and students taught by traditional methods?
- iii. To what extent does the use of e-learning affect academic performance of higher social studies students in terms of gender and location?
- iv. How does the use of e-learning affect the level of motivation of students at the

advanced technical level of social studies and those who are taught in traditional ways?

- v. How does e-learning affect the retention rate of high school social studies students in terms of gender and location?

Method

The research employ a experimental design. The design was appropriate and relevant to investigate the impact of E-learning on social studies students, motivation, retention and academic achievement of upper basic school. The population of the study was 105,810 students in Kwara state. Sample of 480 students were employed for the research through purposive sampling. The instrument for data collection in the study is social studies performance test. The two group were taught for six(6) weeks. At the end of the period, the test was administered, marked and scored for each item. The overall performance was therefore, used to measure the differences between the two groups of students. The data analysis in this study was done by using mean and standard deviation to know the differences between the two groups.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the educational overall performance of Upper Basic Social Studies college students taught the use of e-learning and people taught with traditional approach?

This studies query become spoke back the use of descriptive information of approach and trendy deviations. The end result of the evaluation is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Means and Standard Deviations on UB college students' overall performance in e-mastering and traditional approach

Treatment	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Experimental	240	37.79	11.333	14.042	12.142	15.942
Control	240	23.75	9.796			
Total	480					

Table 1 presents the precis of the Means and Standard Deviations on instructional overall performance of Upper Basic Social Student college students taught the use of e-mastering and people taught with traditional approach. The imply instructional overall performance ratings of the experimental organization (M=37.79, SD=11.333) become excessive than that of the manage organization (M=23.75, SD=9.796). The imply distinction become 14.042 in favors of the experimental organization. The 95% self belief c program language period of the distinction is among 12.142 to 15.942.

Research Question 2:

What is the impact of e-learning on academic performance of students in higher basic social studies in terms of gender and location?

The questions in this survey were answered using descriptive statistics for mean and standard deviation. The analysis results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of UB student e-learning methods related to gender and location

Sex	Location	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Male	Urban	40.362	.943	38.509	42.215
	Rural	27.461	.947	25.600	29.322
Female	Urban	35.387	.912	33.595	37.179
	Rural	20.336	.909	18.551	22.121

Table 2 summarizes the average and standard deviations of upper elementary school performance taught by e-learning by gender and location. The average academic performance score of urban male students (M = 40.362, SE = 0.943) was higher than that of rural male students (M = 27.461, SE = 0.947). The average 95% confidence interval for male urban and rural students ranged from 38.509 to 42.215 and 25.600 to 29.322, respectively. The average academic performance score of female students in urban areas (M = 35.387, SE = 0.912) was higher than the average academic performance score of female students in rural areas (M = 20.336, SE = 0.909). The average 95% confidence interval for female students in urban and rural areas ranged from 33.595 to 37.179 and 18.551 to 22.121, respectively.

Research Question 3:

What is the level of motivation for e-learning students in higher social studies and students taught in traditional ways?

The questions in this survey were answered using descriptive statistics for mean and standard deviation. The analysis results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Means and Standard Deviations on motivation level of UB students in Social Studies

Treatment	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Experimental	240	74.92	2.881	.170	-.372	.713
Control	240	74.75	2.888			
Total	480					

Table 3 summarizes the average and standard deviations of motivational levels of upper elementary school social studies students taught using e-learning and students taught using traditional methods. The average motivational value of the experimental group (M = 74.92, SD = 2.881) is higher than the average motivational value of the control group (M = 74.75, SD = 2.888). The mean difference favored by the experimental group was 0.170. The 95% confidence interval for the difference ranged from 0.372 to 0.713. Therefore, students who taught social studies using e-learning were more motivated than students who were taught using traditional methods.

Research Question 4:

How long is the memory retention of students in higher social studies taught in e-learning and students taught in traditional ways? The questions in this survey were answered using descriptive statistics for mean and standard deviation. The analysis results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of Retention Levels of UB Students in Social Studies

Treatment	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Experimental	240	35.91	11.915	14.533	12.682	16.385
Control	240	21.38	8.433			
Total	480					

Table 4 summarizes the average and standard deviations of retention levels for social high school students taught using e-learning and students taught using traditional methods. The mean retention of the experimental group (M = 35.91, SD = 11.915) is higher than the mean retention of the control group (M = 21.38, SD = 8.433). The mean difference in favor of the experimental group was 14.533. The 95% confidence interval for the difference ranged from 12.682 to 16.385. Therefore, students who taught social studies using e-learning retained more social science concepts than those taught using traditional methods.

Discussion

Research Question 1

What is the academic performance of students in higher social studies taught in e-learning and students taught in traditional ways? This result is based on the findings of Zarie Zavaraki and Rezaei (2011). Tegegne (2014); Zare, Sarikhani, Sarikhani and Babazadeh (2015); Wong and Ng (2016); Zare, show that e-learners are significantly different from traditional learners. In this way, information and communication

technology is changing the way education is delivered, and e-learning is becoming a viable alternative to traditional classroom education and learning processes. However, the findings show that during the experiment, there was no difference between traditional learning and ICT-enhanced learning in terms of student performance, with all the strengths and weaknesses of Sibanda and Donnelly (2014) Tegegne. It was inconsistent with the result of (2014).

Research Question 2

To what extent does the use of e-learning affect academic performance of higher social studies students in terms of gender and location? This discovery confirms the results of Chen, Lambert and Guidry (2010). Alocan and Arigesuyo (2013); Naqvi and Naqvi (2017) showed no significant difference in student performance in terms of gender or school location. Thus, there was a positive link between the use of e-learning technology and the student's academic performance in terms of gender and location in the field of study. However, this study contradicts Ngwu's (2015) finding that only boys'school

students achieve higher average grades than girls' school students. Also, a survey by Opoku Asare and Siaw (2015). Akinwumi (2017) showed that urban students performed better than schools in rural and urban areas.

Research Question 3

How does the use of e-learning affect the level of motivation of students at the advanced technical level of social studies and those who are taught in traditional ways? In this study, I knew that there was no significant difference between the motivational motivation of the student, which was taught the people taught by the Empire and the people taught by the traditional way. This result has been agreed on the survey results of Rovai, Ponton, Wighting, Baker (2007) have all concurred on this outcome. However, discovery did not support the results of Wan, Wang and Haggelty (2008). People and Meyer (2010). Kim and flick (2011). This discloses that ELEARNING statements have a significant impact on the business results of the students as conventional teaching methods. Furthermore, this study finds a big difference between the average motivation of the upper basic social research, which teaches students fantastically from the point of view of gender and place. This decision supports the results of BLUM (2005). Garland and Martin (2005). Cuadrado garcía, Ruiz molina and Montoroponson (2010). OKORIE (2014); Arbabisarjou, Zare, Shahrakipour and Ghoreihinia (2016); Gender and gender and situation are important Basri, Alandejani and Almadani (2018) are an important variable that affects student academic grades. In addition, urban schools are usually endowed with the physical resources needed to enhance learning. However, this finding is in contrast to the results of Davies and Graff (2005). Neema Abooki and Kitawi (2014) showed that e-learning strategies did not significantly differ in academic performance of students in terms of gender and location.

Research Question 4

How does e-learning affect the retention rate of high school social studies students in terms of gender and location? This study found a significant difference between the average retention scores of high school social studies students taught in e-learning and those taught in

traditional ways. This is consistent with the findings of Samuel and Peter (2013). AlQahtani and Higgins (2013); Giannousi, Vernadakis, Derri, Antoniou, Kioumurtzoglou (2014); Giovengo (2014); Sisco, Woodcock and Eady (2015); Banditvilai (2016); Gambari, Shittu, Ogunlade, and Osunlade (2017). showed that there was a significant difference in retention scores between students taught using e-learning and students taught using traditional methods. This means using e-learning technology to provide students with diverse learning, display more information, and increase retention rates. As a result of Mooneyhan (2012); Elmer, Carter, Armga, and Carter (2016) hold between students taught using e-learning strategies and students taught using traditional methods. It did not show a significant difference.

Finally, in this study, there was no significant difference in the average retention scores of students in the sixth form of social studies taught in e-learning in terms of gender and location. This discovery confirmed the results of Lee, Yeh, Kung and Hsu (2007). Timothy (2008) and Berteau (2009) did not show a significant difference in the average retention scores of students taught in gender- and location-related educational approaches. On the contrary, Koochang, (2004); Askar, Altun and Ilgaz (2008); Mahmoud, Ahmed and Mirna (2012) significantly differed in the average retention score of students taught using e-learning strategies in terms of gender and location. Reported that there is.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Researchers have made conclusions and recommendation based on the results of their studies.

The students who taught social studies using an e-learning approach were academically superior to those taught using traditional methods at high schools in Kwara State. With e-learning, it was discovered in Upper Basic, Kwara, that students who taught social studies could compete academically favorably, regardless of gender or location. Researchers have found that teaching is not the deciding factor in the academic motivation of students studying social studies in high schools in Kwara. Although there were significant differences between the two groups, it is noteworthy that the recall levels of students taught using e-learning were higher than those taught

using traditional methods. increase. Therefore, the e-learning approach can be used to teach social studies in high school.

Curriculum reviews by the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) should be conducted to reflect the dynamics of e-learning applications at all levels of high school social studies. This promotes a student-centric approach to education, student autonomy in knowledge acquisition, and student self-discovery learning. Social studies teachers need to be trained by the Kwara State Government and NGOs on the basic skills to use e-learning techniques. This helps improve student performance regardless of gender or location in high school in the state. The Kwara State Government seeks partnerships with private and non-governmental organizations to provide e-learning equipment such as laptops and desktop computers to motivate students to use e-learning techniques in state high schools. need to do it. The Ministry of Education of Kwara needs to institutionalize the use of e-learning techniques by providing secondary schools with appropriate e-learning capabilities. This helps improve the retention capacity of state high school students.

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